

Isorhamnetin-7-O- β -D-galactoside from***Tagetes patula***

A. K. TRIPATHI*

Chemistry Department, Government Science P. G. College,
Bilaspur-495 001

and

M. K. PALIWAL and J. SINGH

Natural Product Laboratory, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 31 July 1991, accepted 4 December 1991

TAGETES patula Linn. (Asteraceae) is known to contain thiophenes, 6-hydroxyflavonoids and carotenoids¹ and is cultivated as garden ornamental². In the course of our investigations on the biologically active constituents of Indian traditional medicines, we have isolated a new flavone glycoside from the flowers.

The shade-dried flowers of *T. patula* (3.6 kg, collected from a local garden, a voucher specimen is at B.S.I., Allahabad) were extracted with 90% ethanol. The *in vacuo* concentrated extract was partitioned with solvents of increasing polarity. The ethyl acetate-soluble portion was chromatographed on silica gel column and eluted with increasing proportions of ethyl acetate in chloroform, ethyl acetate and ethyl acetate-methanol mixtures. The EtOAc-MeOH (8 : 2) eluate furnished a solid when observed on the second day. It was discarded and the supernatant liquid was concentrated, which again yielded some yellowish gummy solid when kept in a refrigerator for one week. It was washed with ethyl acetate and taken up in methanol. Upon chromatography on cellulose plates, a yellow spot ($R_f=42$) followed by a tailed impurity was noted. The less polar fraction was purified by preparative tlc and was crystallised from methanol as light yellow

crystals (80 mg), m.p. 206–08°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 255, 270sh, 305sh, 355; (+NaOMe) 240sh, 275, 290sh, 405; (+AlCl₃) 270, 302sh, 398; (+AlCl₃/HCl) 265, 270, 300sh, 358, 395; (+NaOAc) 253, 267sh, 304, 355; (NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 255, 270sh, 306sh, 355nm. The compound appeared dark purple under uv changing to yellow when exposed with ammonia vapours. Hydrolysis with 6% HCl (4 h) afforded a aglycone, identified as isorhamnetin (by m.p., uv, ir, pmr and mass spectra)³. The sugar was found to be galactose by comparison with an authentic sample, $R_f=0.44$ (n-BuOH-pyridine-water, 6 : 4 : 3), the osazone, m.p. 183°. The diagnostic uv shifts of the glycoside when compared with that of the aglycone, revealed the glycosylation at position-7. The pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆; 90 MHz) displayed signals at δ 6.45 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.50 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.98 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-5'), 7.60 (1H, dd, J 2 and 8 Hz, H-6'), 7.95 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2'), 3.90 (s, OCH₃), 5.25 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1" galactosyl) and 3.20–3.80 (6H, complex multiplet, sugar protons).

On the basis of the above observations, and also the fact⁴ that since the permethylated glycoside upon hydrolysis gave identical 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methylgalactose obtained by similar manner from lactose, its structure was assigned as isorhamnetin-7-O- β -D-galactopyranoside.

Acknowledgement

The work was carried out by the warm encouragement of the former Principal Dr. H. N. Tewary to whom the authors express sincere regards. Thanks to Dr. D. S. Bhakuni, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for the spectral data and to Prof. H. P. Tewari, University of Allahabad, for his kind interest in the work.

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